

Frequency of Usage of Conversational AI Support and its Relations with Emotion Regulation Strategies: A Gender-based Comparative Study among Boys and Girls

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AI chatbots are rapidly integrating into the daily routines of young individuals, serving purposes such as information retrieval, academic assistance, and emotional support. So, our study aims to determine how the frequency of AI chatbot usage is related to two emotion regulation styles: cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression, and whether these patterns differ across males and females. Participants were 72 young Indian adults (36 boys & 36 girls) aged 18 to 30. We collected data using a self-constructed questionnaire to find AI chatbot usage frequency and standardized Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ-30; Preece & Gross, 2026). Pearson's correlation results reveal no association between AI usage frequency and cognitive reappraisal ($r = -0.048$; $p = 0.691$) and no correlation with expressive suppression ($r = 0.001$; $p = 0.995$). The T-test results indicate that there was no significant difference in the frequency of AI usage between males ($M=3.36$, $SD=0.833$) and females ($M=3.19$, $SD=0.786$), $t = 0.873$, $p = 0.193$. The analysis also showed that there is no significant difference in use of cognitive reappraisal, with males ($M = 14.83$, $SD = 4.025$) and females ($M = 15.19$, $SD = 4.275$) reporting similar levels, $t = -0.369$, $p = 0.357$. However, analysis reveals a significant gender difference in use of expressive suppression, $t = 1.766$, $p = 0.041$, between males ($M = 15.17$, $SD = 3.692$) and females ($M = 13.42$, $SD = 4.662$). The findings show that males and females use AI and cognitive reappraisal at similar levels, and males use expressive suppression more than females. Results also show that AI usage is associated with lower cognitive reappraisal and higher expressive suppression.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, emotional regulation strategies, ChatGPT

Artificial Intelligence has emerged as a great innovation in recent times. It is gradually changing how societies function by improving accuracy, effectiveness and decision-making in several areas, like finding healthcare solutions, and others, enabling robots to mimic human intelligence, encompassing learning, thinking, problem-solving and creativity. Although these systems do not possess emotions, their capacity to produce human-like responses allows them to provide emotionally supportive interactions by using validation, reassurance, and cognitive re-framing. Therefore, they can function as accessible solutions of emotional support by engaging users in reflective dialogue that mirrors key emotion regulation strategies.

Emotion regulation consists of methods used by people to change how they experience or express emotions. People can use different types of strategies to manage their emotions, and these strategies have important consequences for mental health (Preece et al., 2025). It includes processes, which may be deliberate or automatic, through which individuals monitor, evaluate, and modify the intensity,

duration, and expression of their emotional experiences. This helps them to adapt to situational demands, promote psychological well-being, and achieve personal and social goals (Gross & Thompson, 2007). Some of the principal adaptive emotion regulation strategies are cognitive reappraisal (the meaning of emotion-generating situations is reinterpreted), problem-solving (addressing the problems that are creating emotional distress), and seeking social support (taking assistance from other people). Some of the maladaptive emotion regulation strategies are expressive suppression (not talking about or not expressing emotions in behaviors) and avoidance (withdrawing from emotion-provoking situations). Much research has shown that using adaptive emotion regulation strategies, such as re-framing of thoughts is associated with better mental health (Dawel et al., 2024). On the other hand, using maladaptive strategies like suppressing our feelings and avoidance is related to poorer psychological health outcomes (ERQ-30; Preece & Gross, 2026).

Theoretical Background: Emotion Regulation

Many theories explain emotion regulation. One such theory is James Gross's Process Model of Emotion Regulation (1998). According to it, emotion regulation is a step-by-step process. And there are two broad strategies. Antecedent-focused strategies are used before emotions can fully arise, such as when we try to reframe a stressful deadline as an opportunity for growth or learning (Yarwood, 2022). It calls strategies applied afterwards response-focused strategies (e.g., when we force a smile even when frustrated). So, when we use an antecedent-focused strategy as a priority, it results in better

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adaptation/regulation than using response-focused tactics (Yarwood, 2022). Neuroimaging and other studies have also confirmed that cognitive reinterpretation is much better than suppression for mental well-being (e.g., an intentional shift in our mindset helps lower anxiety; suppressing our feelings creates outbursts) (Feng et al., 2025).

Figure 1

James Gross's Process Model of Emotion Regulation (1998)

In recent AI chatbot, designs, techniques like CBT have been included. CBT is commonly used to modify thinking patterns and behaviors related to emotional states (Farzan et al., 2024).

The US-based Pew Research Center (2025) conducted a survey in which they found that AI chatbots are becoming more common in daily life. According to it, 31% of teenagers use AI chat bots daily. 16% of them reported frequent or constant use. The most widely used chatbot is ChatGPT (59%), its usage rate is more than double that of Gemini (23%) and Meta AI (20%) (Atske, 2025). Feng et al. (2025) found in their systematic review and meta-analysis that generative AI chat bots had the highest effect size in reducing overall mental suffering. It also promotes healthy behavior change.

AI chatbots for mental support helped reduce depression and anxiety scores and improved emotional intelligence dimensions, like self-awareness and emotional regulation (Rawat, 2025). Participants' decision-making improved, and impulsivity declined. All these results were seen in research by Rawat (2025). This suggests regular human-AI interactions can positively affect perception of emotions and self-regulation. Some participants here said that AI chatbots felt like friends and they understood their emotions; others feared becoming emotionally reliant on AI (Rawat, 2025).

Most AI conversational agents these days are used to give therapy and psycho-education support. According to Li et al. (2023), some have been giving emotional comfort or companionship to lonely people. People with severe symptoms also found conversational agents very useful. Although these people still preferred human help. That means, there's a need to identify till when chatbots are enough and when real, professional support becomes important. A lot of users also said they had good experiences with AI chatbots-- they felt like it understood them and emotionally connected with them (Li et al., 2023). But some also gave negative feedback. They said that they couldn't feel emotional depth in the responses, or the agent misunderstood them. Some people said they felt AI was emotionally

distant (Li et al., 2023).

Studies have shown that as men and women, we differ in how we connect emotionally and how we handle emotions. According to Zaia et al. (2025), women mostly looked for support. They express feelings. Men, on the other hand, were seen to suppress or focus on problem-solving. One reason could be social and cultural expectations around them- shaping these patterns. Differences are also seen in the way different genders are engaging with mental health support like generative AI. Variations in their style of interactions have been noticed (Mayor, 2025).

Mogelvang et al. (2024) also found that gender differences even existed in the purposes for which people use AI. They are used by men mostly as functional tools to increase their productivity and for job finding. Women mostly use them to explore creative ideas. Even the way women describe their experiences with chatbots is different it is more emotional and reflective. They focused on personal feelings more. They also had greater concerns about using AI. They were afraid that it would make them more dependent and weaken their thinking skills.

So, we can say that both genders are not just different in emotion management-they often do so in different ways. Women mostly prefer to think things through or reframe situations. Many of them also find venting helpful. Men use fewer approaches. Sobieska et al. (2025) found in their review study that women are more likely to use rumination compared to men. Some other studies didn't find much difference. Having said that, even if people are using similar methods, how effective they would be and the brain processes behind them these can differ.

When it comes to cognitive reappraisal strategies-meaning trying to look at a situation from a different angle- Kakollu et al. (2026) found women using them more often than men. Although these findings aren't always consistent. Though a worrying trend was seen in these studies. Nearly 42% young adults today moderately or highly suppress their feelings (Kakollu et al., 2026).

Perchtold et al. (2019) found that men and women are actually equally capable of rethinking situations and coming up with healthier interpretations. Also, their styles of reinterpreting are similar. Like finding positives, making "light" of an embarrassing situation, or focusing on finding solutions. Then where's the difference? The real difference, as seen, was in their confidence and how often they used them. Men felt more capable using these strategies. Women, on the other hand, doubted their ability and used them less. Now, this affected the benefits to each gender. It was seen that such reappraisal protected men more clearly from depression. The benefit for women was weaker (Perchtold et al., 2019).

Several studies conclude that AI chatbots are a promising tool if we want to give mental care to people with mild to moderate conditions. But, going forward, we must prioritize improvement of their therapeutic potential. Also, Privacy risks need to be reduced too.

Literature Gap and Research Rationale

Although companies and researchers widely promote AI chatbots for emotional support, we don't really know much about how their frequent usage could relate to emotion management/ coping strategies.

Very few researches have been done on AI chatbot usage and

emotional coping in Indian populations, particularly among young adults (Chaudhuri, 2024). We also haven't really studied whether this relation works differently for men and women, even though we already know they handle emotions in different ways. Another issue is that most AI chatbots still don't feel relatable to Indian people. Since they are built using Western data and ideas, they don't always fit well in the Indian context. So, there is a need to design a culturally sensitive chatbot. Filling these gaps matters a lot. If we understand these, we can improve chatbot design, which can prevent over-dependence on them. We can make digital mental-health tools more sensitive to gender differences also. So, in our study, we try to explore how often young Indian men and women use AI chatbots and how that relates to the way they handle their emotions.

Aim To examine the frequency of AI conversational support and its relation with emotion regulation strategies (specific focus on Cognitive reappraisal & Expressive suppression) among boys and girls in India.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: There is a statistically significant relationship between the frequency of AI chatbot/conversational usage and emotion regulation strategies (cognitive reappraisal & expressive suppression) among young adults in India.
- *H2*: There is a statistically significant difference in the frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents between male and female young adults in India.
- *H3*: There is a statistically significant difference between male and female young adults in the adoption of 'cognitive reappraisal' and 'expressive suppression' strategies for emotional regulation.

Method

Participants

Total of 72 young Indian adults, 18-30-year-old participated, out of which 36 were boys and 36 were girls. The sample included college-going students and young adults employed in different industries. We excluded young adults who didn't use AI chatbots on personal devices. We used a convenience sampling technique to collect the data.

Research Design

We employed a two-group, quantitative research design.

Nature: Correlational.

Measures

AI Conversational Support Usage Questionnaire (Self-constructed): This measure has 12 items, including items trying to find the frequency of AI conversational support usage, the purpose of AI usage, how it affected participants' thinking skills and life in general, among others. The item trying to find the frequency of AI conversational support usage was the main item used in our study. We measured this AI chatbot usage frequency using an ordinal 4-point response scale, by assigning numerical codes (1-4) to the response categories. These codes were used for data entry and analysis in SPSS. For example, response category: "Almost constantly/Several times a day" was assigned 4 points, "Several times a week" was assigned 3 points, "Once a month" was given 2 points, and "Less than once a month" was assigned 1 point. Higher scores indicated more frequent AI chatbot usage. Reliability analysis

showed Cronbach's Alpha coefficient as 0.719.

Emotional Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ-30) (Preece & Gross, 2026): This is a self-report measure of emotion regulation with 30 items. It is a 7-point rating scale that ranges from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 7 (*strongly agree*). The questionnaire scores for the frequency of usage of 10 different emotion regulation strategies (subscales). They are a combination of adaptive and maladaptive strategies. A higher score on a subscale represents a greater usage frequency of that particular emotion regulation strategy. Scores for each sub-scale are calculated by adding up scores of the items that represent it.

Ethical Considerations

We obtained informed consent from the participants before collecting data. We maintained confidentiality of the participants.

Statistical Analyses

Our study employed descriptive statistics like Mean and Standard deviation to describe the characteristics of the data. We used inferential statistics to examine differences and relationships among the variables. T-test was used to determine significant differences between groups. We used Pearson correlation analysis to examine the nature and strength of the relationships between the variables.

Results

The internal consistency reliability of our study came out to be good, with a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.719.

Figure 2

Frequency of AI Usage among Females

Figure 3

Frequency of AI Usage among Males

We used SPSS analysis to compare the frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents between males and females. We found that the mean AI usage frequency among males is 3.36, $SD = 0.833$. The mean AI usage frequency among females is 3.19, $SD = 0.786$.

Pie charts comparing frequency of AI usage between both genders indicate that among females ($N=36$), 89% had high frequency of AI chatbot usage (36% out of the total ($N=36$) using it 'almost constantly/several times a day,' 53% out of the total ($N=36$) using it

'several times in a week'). Females with a low frequency of AI chatbot usage was 11% (5% using it 'once a month,' 6% using it 'less than once a month').

Among males ($N=36$), 89% reported a high frequency of AI chatbot usage (which is similar to females). Here, the percentages were reversed: 53% of males ($N=36$) used it 'almost constantly/several times a day' and 36% of the males ($N=36$) used it 'several times in a week'. We found that the percentage of males in the low-frequency AI chatbot usage category was the same as that of females.

Table 1

Pearson Correlations among Frequency of AI Chat-bot Use and Emotional Regulation Strategies ($N=72$)

Variable	Frequency of usage of AI chat-bots/conversational agents	Cognitive reappraisal	Expressive suppression
Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents	1	-0.048	0.001
Emotional Regulation			
Cognitive reappraisal	-0.048	1	0.231
Expressive suppression	0.001	0.231	1

Note. Pearson correlation coefficients are reported. None of the correlations were statistically significant ($p > .05$)

Correlation analyses showed a weak negative correlation between 'Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents' and 'Cognitive reappraisal' ($r = -0.048$; $p = 0.691$), since the p value is less than 0.05, so it is not a statistically significant relationship between frequency of AI chatbots and cognitive reappraisal. Similarly, there

is no statistically significant relationship between 'Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents' and 'Expressive suppression' ($r = 0.001$; $p = 0.995$). The correlation between 'cognitive reappraisal' and 'expressive suppression' is weak positive ($r = 0.231$, $p = 0.051$), but it is not statistically significant.

Table 2

Shows MEAN & SD

	Responders							
	Males				Females			
	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error of Mean	N	Mean	SD	Std. Error of Mean
Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents	36	3.36	0.833	0.139	36	3.19	0.786	0.131
Emotional Regulation								
Cognitive Reappraisal	36	14.83	4.025	0.671	36	15.19	4.275	0.712
Expressive Suppression	36	15.17	3.692	0.615	36	13.42	4.662	0.777

Table 3

Independent Samples t-Test Result for AI Chatbot Usage and Emotional Regulation

	t	p
Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents	0.873	0.193
Emotional Regulation		
Cognitive reappraisal	-0.369	0.357
Expressive Suppression	1.766	0.041

Note. $N=72$, Independent samples t-test results are presented. Statistical significance was determined at the .05 level ($p < .05$)

With the help of the t-test for independent groups, we found that the frequency of AI usage among males ($M=3.36$, $SD=0.833$) compared to that among females ($M=3.19$, $SD=0.786$) demonstrated no significant difference, $t = 0.873$, $p = 0.193$.

We used independent samples t-test to compare the usage of

emotional regulation strategies (specifically cognitive reappraisal & expressive suppression) between males and females. Our analysis showed that there was no significant difference in adoption of the cognitive reappraisal strategy, $t = -0.369$, $p = 0.357$, when comparing males ($M = 14.83$, $SD = 4.025$) and females ($M = 15.19$, $SD = 4.275$). When comparing adoption of the expressive suppression strategy, our analysis showed a significant difference, $t = 1.766$, $p = 0.041$, with males showing a higher level ($M = 15.17$, $SD = 3.692$) than females ($M = 13.42$, $SD = 4.662$). Therefore, there is no significant difference between males and females in AI usage frequency and adoption of the cognitive reappraisal strategy. On the other hand, there exists a significant difference between males and females in the adoption of the expressive suppression strategy for emotional regulation.

Discussion

Our research aims to study the frequency of AI conversational

support and its relation with emotion regulation strategies (cognitive reappraisal & expressive suppression) among boys and girls in India.

Our analysis indicates that the majority of young adults use AI chatbots frequently, several times per week. Usage frequency in males is slightly higher than that of females, although t-test results showed no statistically significant difference. The percentage of participants with very low chatbot usage frequency (once a month/lesser than once a month) was same for both genders. Our findings show that there isn't a significant difference in frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents between males and females. This might be due to the fact that young males and females today have almost equal access to technology, internet and education, they have comparable digital literacy, which leads to similar usage patterns among both genders. AI chatbot technology has changed from specialized tools to become everyday utility tools. Another reason could be similar developmental demands of this age group - academic, career and productivity pressures which could motivate similar usage patterns across genders.

We examined the relationship between frequency of AI usage and emotion regulation strategies (Cognitive reappraisal & Expressive suppression) through Correlation analysis. Our results indicated a weak negative correlation between 'Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents' and Cognitive Reappraisal, though it was not significant. So, there is no relationship between the frequency of AI chat bot usage and cognitive reappraisal strategy (changing our way of thinking about a situation so that emotions associated with it also transform) and the use of AI chatbots does not influence how an individual with reanalysis/reinterpret emotional situations. The reason for the above result might be as in the questionnaire assessing frequency of AI chat bot use, the majority of students reported that they use AI chat bot for educational purpose (information seeking, doing assessments, getting creating ideas for projects) and entertainment, rather than dealing with their emotional well being, mostly students reported that they never rely on AI chatbot for emotional support or never use AI chatbot when facing with emotional issues/ distress so, usage of AI chat bot is not affecting the cognitive processes required for emotional reinterpretation in using cognitive reappraisal strategy. Similarly, we found no correlation between 'Frequency of usage of AI chatbots/conversational agents' and Expressive Suppression. This indicates that the frequency of AI usage does not affect or influence individuals' level of emotional suppression strategies. Our results are consistent with research by Gandhi and Singh (2024) which states that various psychological and individual factors influence use of different emotional regulation strategies, rather than just the frequency of AI chat bot usage. Individual's usage of emotional regulation strategies is determined by various factors like their personality traits, societal pressure/norms and various other abilities, so it cannot be affected only by the use of AI chat bot. Also, individuals are using AI for educational purposes primarily, not much for emotional support.

We used independent samples t-test to compare the usage of emotional regulation strategies (specifically, cognitive reappraisal & Emotion Suppression) between males and females. Our analysis showed no significant difference in use of cognitive reappraisal strategy between males and females. The reason for this result might be that males and females in recent times receive somewhat similar schooling, digital exposure, and problem-solving exposure leading both genders to re-interpret their situations similarly. Also,

reappraisal uses memory, executive, abstract reasoning and perspective taking skills, which are capacities that don't differ much between genders in adulthood. In modern urban landscape, greater mental health awareness is changing how genders socialize, with both genders being encouraged to understand their emotions rather than turning a blind eye to them. These findings of our study support existing literature, which found that men and women exhibit similar basic capacities of creating cognitive reappraisals. Perchtold et al. (2019) found that both genders use similar ways of re-interpreting situations. And both genders showed no difference in their usage of the cognitive reinterpretation strategy (Asawa et al., 2025).

When comparing 'usage of Expressive suppression strategy', our analysis indicates a significant difference between both genders. Males showed a higher Mean frequency of usage of Expressive suppression as an emotion regulation strategy than females. Our results support our hypothesis - there is a statistically significant difference between frequency of usage of Expressive suppression among male and female young adults. The reason for males showing a higher frequency of adoption of Expressive suppression than females might be because of societal norms/stereotypes that expect men to always "be/seem strong" and label emotional expression/sensitivity among men as "weakness". Females in Indian society don't usually have to deal with the same expectations; they can talk/vent to their friends and express emotions, even cry when they need to, without the risk of being labelled as "weak". Our findings align with recent research evidence, which shows that males show a higher dependence on and usage of expressive suppression to manage their emotions (Asawa et al., 2025).

Conclusion

Overall, the findings of this research conclude that AI chatbot behavior has become common in this population, with most young adults using them several times a week or more. Our analysis found no gender difference in AI usage frequency. It indicates that AI technologies have slowly become gender-neutral. Almost equal access to technology, similar education and career-related demands, along with similar digital literacy between both genders in this age group could be contributing to this similarity.

When it comes to understanding the relationship of AI usage frequency with emotion regulation patterns, our study found that currently, people use AI mostly for educational purposes, not much for emotional support. There is no association between frequency of AI usage and use of emotional regulation strategies.

Future research could be made better by following people over a longer period of time to see what the long-term emotional effects of relying on AI are. In future studies, objective techniques that directly measure behaviour of a person instead of just asking people about their experiences could lead to better findings. The different usage purposes of AI by people should also be highlighted, like for academic help, internet surfing, or supporting themselves emotionally. Finally, AI tools should be shaped in ways that encourage healthier coping, and not passive dependence. Since they are becoming a regular part of our daily life, it's important to understand them well. And this includes also finding out how it influences people's processing and managing of emotions. This will help make these technologies more psychologically safe and responsible.

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